

The United Arab Emirates and Humanitarian Aid: A Model of Global Solidarity

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Abstract

This paper looking to the humanitarian aid efforts of the United Arab Emirates (UAE) from a global perspective. As one of the world's leading donors, the country has extended its role in international aid, concentrating on areas such as disaster relief, health aid, infrastructure development, and refugee assistance. This article mostly explores at the UAE's historical context, motivations, key initiatives, and its global impact, discusses how humanitarian initiatives are strengthen the UAE's global standing while providing essential support to vulnerable population worldwide. It also analyzing the UAE's role in encouraging international solidarity, supporting sustainable development, and enhancing its global reputation.

Keywords - UAE, humanitarian aid, global solidarity, sustainable development

Introduction

In the past two decades, the United Arab Emirates has established itself as a prominent leading global donor in the humanitarian efforts, and it's recognized by the United Nations and other international organizations for the UAE's aid contributions. As a young nation, the country's growth in humanitarianism and international philanthropy proves its dedication to helping global development, welfare, and stability.

As per the foreign policy, humanitarian efforts allow the UAE to enhance diplomatic relations and encourage goodwill. This article looks at the diverse dimensions of the UAE's humanitarian aid efforts, partnerships, and motivations. Finally, the paper looks at the impact of the UAE's aid efforts and their alignment with global humanitarian goals in the modern era.

Historical Context of UAE's Humanitarian Aid Initiatives

The humanitarian aid journey of the United Arab Emirates is inspired in the values given by its founding father, His Highness Sheikh Zayed bin Sultan Al Nahyan, whose principles of charity and responsibility have influenced the nation's approach to international aid efforts. In the beginning of the UAE, aid efforts were focused mainly in the Middle East.

At the beginning of the 21st century, the UAE economy developed more than before. So, the UAE started to spread its humanitarian values and aid from a global perspective. This expansion became a significant step in the formation of the Emirates Red Crescent, which helps to mobilize resources and deliver humanitarian aid globally. The UAE's official aid programs are constantly increasing support for countries in South Asia, Africa, and even Latin America. This humanitarian contribution

promoted the UAE's vision of establishing itself as a global humanitarian leader, which solidified through different organizations like the Sheikh Mohammed Bin Rashid Al Maktoum's Foundation and the Khalifa bin Zayed Al Nahyan Foundation.

Motivations of UAE's Humanitarian Aid Efforts

The UAE's humanitarian aid efforts are motivated by the humanitarian values of the nation. The Islamic principle of charity, known as zakat (compulsory giving), is an important cultural motivator that promotes the UAE to deliver support to needy people, regardless of religion, nationality, or ethnicity.

The UAE's international aid initiatives have secured an outstanding position within the global community, projecting an image of a responsible, modern, and benevolent nation. Moreover, international humanitarian aid drove the UAE to strengthen its cultural values and sustainable development to reduce human suffering in the world.

International Collaborations and Strategic Partnerships for Aid

The humanitarian aid efforts of the UAE are mostly conducted in partnership with prominent international organizations, which strengthens its role as a collaborative actor in international philanthropy. The partnerships of the UAE with international organizations such as the United Nations, the Red Crescent, and the World Food Programme (WFP) have been involved in amplifying the effectiveness and reach of the UAE's humanitarian aid initiatives.

During the International donor conference on Yemen in 2023, Her Excellency Noura Al Kaabi, Minister of State, UAE, declared the UAE's commitment to assisting the Yemeni people, stating that "since 2015, the UAE has provided Yemen with a total of USD 6.6 billion in aid and a USD 300 million deposit to bolster the local currency. Continuing this approach, and in addition to multilateral peace and development efforts in Yemen, the UAE is also supporting reconstruction and rehabilitation projects this year with approximately USD 325 million to improve the healthcare, renewable energy, and agriculture sectors, including a major project to build a dam for irrigation purposes."¹

Regional collaborations are also significant to the UAE's humanitarian efforts. As a member of the GCC (Gulf Cooperation Council), the UAE works constantly with other countries of the council to manage humanitarian aid efforts in the Middle East and North Africa. These collaborations not only develop the efficiency of humanitarian aid distribution but also encourage regional solidarity and collective action in addressing humanitarian crises in modern times.

Furthermore, the UAE's diplomatic network has been increased to facilitate aid delivery in politically sensitive areas, demonstrating the strategic nature of its humanitarian approaches.

According to the government website www.u.ae, the following government entities are listed for charitable, humanitarian, and social activities within and outside the country.

¹ <https://www.mofa.gov.ae/en/mediahub/news/2023/2/27/27-02-2023-uae>

1. Ministry of Community Development
2. Ministry of Foreign Affairs
3. Zakat Fund
4. National Emergency Crisis and Disaster Management Authority.
5. National Rehabilitation Centre
6. General Authority of Islamic Affairs and Endowments
7. Islamic Affairs & Charitable Activities Department
8. Community Development Authority
9. Authority of Social Contribution – Ma'an
10. Abu Dhabi Social Support Authority
11. Jood - Dubai's community contributions platform

Charitable organizations in the UAE:

1. Emirates Charity portal
2. Khalifa Bin Zayed Al Nahyan Foundation
3. Zayed Bin Sultan Al Nahyan Charitable and Humanitarian Foundation
4. Emirates Red Crescent Authority
5. Sheikh Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum's foundations
6. Mohammed Bin Rashid Al Maktoum Global Initiatives
7. Al Maktoum Foundation
8. Dubai Charity Association
9. Dubai Cares
10. Noor Dubai
11. Dar Al Ber Society
12. Beit Al Khair Society
13. Emirates Foundation
14. Charitable associations in Dubai - Islamic Affairs and Charitable Activities in Dubai (IACAD)
15. Organizations to volunteer with - Dubai Humanitarian
16. Sharjah Charity International
17. Sharjah City for Humanitarian Services
18. International Charity Organization-Ajman
19. Fujairah Charity Association
20. Al Ihsan Charity Association (Ajman)
21. Sheikh Saud bin Saqr Al Qasimi Foundation for Policy Research (Ras Al Khaimah)
22. Zayed Giving Initiative - the official portal of Abu Dhabi Government
23. Charitable organizations in Ras Al Khaimah - the official portal of Ras Al Khaimah Government
24. UAE Water Foundation (Suqia)
25. Volunteers.ae

Humanitarian organizations for women:

26. Abu Dhabi Center for Shelter and Humanitarian Care – Ewaa
27. Dubai Foundation for Women & Children.

In addition, several philanthropic activities are introduced by UAE leaders such as “Dubai Humanitarian” founded in 2003 by His Highness Sheikh Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum, vice-president and Prime Minister of the United Arab Emirates and Ruler of Dubai.

Today, Dubai Humanitarian is the largest humanitarian hub in the world, 135,000 square meters in size and located near Al Maktoum Airport and close to Jebel Ali Port. This strategic location helps to move the shipment from sea to air within 10 minutes.

(Table 1: The outbound report of Dubai Humanitarian – 2024, Source: Humanitarian Logistics Databank-2024, <https://dubaihumanitarian.ae/databank/>)

In 2025, the stock value of Dubai Humanitarian reached \$205.8 million, which proves the potential of the aid efforts of the UAE.

(Table 2: Humanitarian Logistics Databank, January 2025 Source: <https://dubaihumanitarian.ae/databank/>)

Significant Areas of UAE’s Humanitarian Aid Initiatives

Disaster Relief

The UAE has an extraordinary history of providing quick and significant disaster relief aid regionally and globally. For example, the UAE was among the first responders after Hurricane Dorian struck the Bahamas in 2019, sending help with immediate recovery efforts. Similarly, the UAE responded immediately to the catastrophic earthquake in Nepal in 2015, providing millions of dollars in disaster funds, supplying food, water, and shelter, and sending medical teams.

The UAE provided aid to natural disaster-affected countries worldwide, such as Burkina Faso, Brazil, Faso, the Philippines, Kenya, Ethiopia, Mauritania, South Africa, Cameroon, and the Ivory Coast.

(Figure 1: Ahmed Juma Al Rumaithi, UAE Ambassador to the Federal Republic of Somalia. The UAE has dispatched 700 tonnes of urgent food supplies to the victims of floods that hit several areas in Somalia,2025. Source: wam)

Eradication of Poverty and Hunger

The UAE's humanitarian aid efforts express its dedication to eradicating hunger and poverty through various initiatives and aid efforts, such as the "1 Billion Meals" campaign of His Highness Sheikh Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum, Vice President, Prime Minister, and Ruler of Dubai, which aims to combat malnutrition and hunger by dispatching food aid to deprived communities across Asia, Africa, and the Middle East.

“Under the UAE's strategic partnership with the G20, H.H. Sheikh Khaled bin Mohamed bin Zayed Al Nahyan, Crown Prince of Abu Dhabi, announced a US\$100 million contribution to the Global Alliance against Hunger and Poverty through the UAE Aid Agency”.²

Refugee Assistance of the UAE

The United Arab Emirates is an important donor to refugee initiatives, especially in response to the refugee crisis in the region. The UAE has a significant collaboration with the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and several international agencies, the UAE is the major contributor of maintaining and establishing refugee camps in the Middle East. Beyond financial aid, the country has also given distinguished supports, such as medicine, infrastructure and food. The UAE's dedication to refugees extends to its part of domestic policy, providing Palestinians and Syrians with access to education, healthcare, and employment.

The political role of the UAE is crucial in the crisis of Palestine. The UAE is constantly supporting the people of Palestine to empower their lives and health. Several projects are delivering to them with support of various international agencies.

According to the UAE Foreign Aid Annual Report 2023, 45% of its Humanitarian Assistance was directed to Palestine.

² <https://www.wam.ae/en/article/b6scmvd-uae-leads-global-humanitarian-efforts-2024>
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(Table 3: Humanitarian Assistance of UAE by countries, Source: UAE Foreign Aid Annual Report 2023)
*in USD millions, and as % of total.

In 2024, “Through Operation Chivalrous Knight 3, the UAE has launched an urgent vaccination campaign in the Gaza Strip, aimed at protecting over 640,000 children from the threat of polio.”³

In the last year, “In Lebanon, Sheikh Mohamed bin Zayed directed a US\$100 million emergency relief package and initiated the “UAE Stands with Lebanon “campaign. The UAE also extended US\$30 million to displaced Lebanese citizens in Syria.”⁴

“In April, the UAE pledged US\$100 million to support humanitarian efforts in Sudan and its neighbouring countries. In Chad, new initiatives were launched, and a US\$10.25 million contribution to the United Nations aimed at supporting Sudanese refugee women affected by the ongoing crisis in the country.”⁵

The UAE has played a crucial role in addressing the humanitarian crisis in Yemen, offering several aids such as establishing field hospitals, supplying clean water, and distributing food provisions to ease the suffering caused by the ongoing conflict.

Economic Development and Infrastructure aid

The UAE has invested millions of Dirhams in infrastructure projects in several countries, mainly in Asia and Africa. These projects are including building hospitals, schools, and clean water facilities in countries like Pakistan, Sudan and Egypt. Moreover, the UAE has donated millions of dollars to help in infrastructure and economic development in East Africa, emphasizing its long-term approach to encourage stability through sustainable development.

³ <https://www.wam.ae/en/article/b6scmvd-uae-leads-global-humanitarian-efforts-2024>

⁴ <https://gulfnews.com/uae/government/uae-leads-global-humanitarian-efforts-in-2024-1.104963862>

⁵ <https://gulfnews.com/uae/government/uae-leads-global-humanitarian-efforts-in-2024-1.104963862>

Health Aid and Pandemic Responses

The role of the UAE in health aid became significant during the COVID-19 pandemic. The UAE sent millions of large-scale vaccines, PPE kit, screening equipment, ventilators, and tons of medical supplies to 135 countries around the world, including the Philippines. These efforts are demonstrating the capacity and willingness of the country to assist the global fight against the crisis of pandemic era, moreover, strengthen the international reputation of the UAE.

Climate and Environmental Initiatives

The UAE has extended its humanitarian support to climate protection and environmental support. After the understanding the vulnerabilities of several countries to climate change, the UAE has proposed distinguished funded initiatives aimed to strengthening climate adaptation, like water conservation projects in many countries affecting deforestation. All the efforts of the UAE align with its dedication to the sustainable development.

At the opening of the World Climate Action Summit (COP28) in Dubai, 2023, H.H. Sheikh Mohamed bin Zayed Al Nahyan, President of the UAE, announced the establishment of a US\$30 billion fund for global climate solutions, and the fund aims to raise US\$250 billion by 2030.

The UAE has introduced notable environmental initiatives, such as the Mohamed bin Zayed Species Conservation Fund.

“In 2024, the latest round of funding ensured that the Fund allocated \$27,143,809 to global species conservation. This support has facilitated 2,894 projects and played a crucial role in bringing 1,789 species back from the brink of extinction.”⁶

(Table 4: Distribution of funds by species type, Source: Annual Report of the Mohamed bin Zayed Species Conservation Fund - 2023)

⁶ <https://www.speciesconservation.org/about-us/>

International Impact of UAE's Humanitarian Efforts

The UAE's contributions of humanitarian efforts have a significant impact on beneficiary countries, developing the lives of millions while improving the UAE's standing on the global stage. The UAE ranks as one of the largest donors relative to its GDP, having distributed billions of dollars recently. This large scale of contributions emphasizes the commitment of UAE to philanthropy and has been recognized by international organizations such as the United Nations.

The UAE's humanitarian aid initiatives have given critical helps in areas such as education, healthcare, and infrastructure. In Syria, for example, UAE-funded projects have supported to rebuild hospitals and schools, supporting with essential services to communities affected by war. Similarly, the funded projects of UAE helped for infrastructure development in Africa has increased access to healthcare, education, and clean water, providing to long-term socioeconomic developments.

The vision of UAE for humanitarian initiatives lines up with its long-term development goals, such as defined in the UAE Vision 2021 and UAE Centennial 2071 Plan. In addition, the country looking to expand its focus on climate adaptation, sustainable development, and technological innovation in aid distribution. By investing in renewable energy and climate resilience, the UAE aims to address the basis causes of humanitarian challenges, providing to a more sustainable future in worldwide for vulnerable populations.

“Since the establishment of the UAE in 1971, until mid-2024, the UAE's foreign aid amounted to AED360 billion (US\$98 billion), having a significant impact on reducing poverty, mitigating the effects of disasters and crises, supporting economic and social development, and promoting international stability and peace.”⁷

During the holy month of Ramadan, distinguished campaigns of the UAE are increasing humanitarian initiatives in the recent years. His Highness Sheikh Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum, Vice President, Prime Minister, and Ruler of Dubai has launched the Mothers' Endowment Campaign in the Ramadan of 2024, which aims to collect AED 1 billion endowment fund, securing help for the education of millions throughout the world.

In conclusion, the UAE has established itself as a global leader in philanthropy, consistently extending support to communities affected by crises and disasters. Through strategic initiatives, including food assistance, healthcare, education, and infrastructure development, the UAE has demonstrated its dedication to reducing human suffering and promoting stability worldwide. The humanitarian efforts not only reflect UAE's values of generosity and compassion but also cements international cooperation and development. As global challenges several crises, the UAE continue its commitments of delivering essential supports and strengthen its role as a most significant contributor to global humanitarian aid efforts.

⁷ <https://www.wam.ae/en/article/b6i89id-uae-foreign-aid-hit-aed-360-billion-since-1971>
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